

Figure S3. Species abundance distribution patterns of the OTUs in the 106 samples. Left panel: occurrence of each microbial OTU plotted against its dispersion index. The dotted line represents the 2.5 % confidence limit of the χ^2 distribution, with frequent OTUs depicted in orange and rare OTUs in blue. Right panel: abundance distribution of frequent and rare OTUs.